

INFLUENCE OF HARVEST STAGE AND STORAGE DURATION ON SEED GERMINATION AND SEEDLING VIGOUR OF HOT PEPPER (*Capsicum annum L.*)

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ABSTRACT

A field and laboratory study was conducted at the Teaching and Research farm as well as the Plant Breeding and Seed Science laboratory of the Joseph Sarwuan Tarka University, Makurdi during the 2023 growing season to evaluate the effects of stages of harvest and seed storage duration on the germination and seedling vigour of hot pepper. Two varieties of hot pepper (Dogo and Rodo) and three harvest stages were the treatments for the field experiment. The field experiment was a 2x3 combination of treatments arranged in a Randomized Complete Block Design (RCBD) replicated three times and was carried out basically to generate seeds for the laboratory study. The laboratory experiment for seed quality evaluation comprised of two varieties of hot pepper (Dogo and Rodo), three harvest stages, and three storage durations all arranged in a Completely Randomized Design (CRD) with three replications. Pepper fruits were harvested at the mature green stage, mature half-red ripe stage and mature full red ripe stage coinciding with (46, 49 and 52 days after anthesis DAA) and stored at 0, 3 and 6 months after which their effects on germination and seedling vigour were evaluated. The physiological seed quality parameters evaluated included germination (%), pre-emergence mortality percentage, seedling vigour, and seedling fresh and dry weight. The result from analysis of variance (ANOVA) showed that seeds of pepper fruits harvested from the mature full red ripe stages exhibited superiority in all the germination and seedling vigour attributes evaluated. Fruits harvested at the mature green stage however, produced seeds with the poorest seed germination and seedling vigour.

Keywords: emergence, germination, mortality, parameters, vigour

INTRODUCTION

Pepper (*Capsicum annum L.*) includes both hot and sweet peppers which belong to the Family of Solanaceae and are mostly herbs and climbers. The family contains about 90 genera and nearly 30 species with *Capsicum annum* and *Capsicum frutescens* commonly grown in Nigeria (Olatunji and Afolayan, 2020). Several

literatures have indicated that pepper is believed to have originated from Central and South America (Safari and Roossinck, 2018) and comprises about 30 species, five of which are domesticated. These include *Capsicum annum L.* (hot and sweet peppers), *Capsicum frutescens L.* or bird pepper, *Capsicum chinense (Jacq)* or aromatic Chili pepper,

Capsicum baccatum (L) and *Capsicum pubescens* (Ruiz and Pav). (rocoto). The first three species are the most cultivated in tropical and temperate zones. *C. annum* often forms a complex with *C. frutescens* and *C. chinense*. In Africa, they are generally considered together as *C. annum* L. (Grubben and El Tahir, 2004). In the tropics, several species of pepper are grown everywhere. Pepper produces fruits of different sizes which are initially green or yellow at physiological maturity and red when ripe (Grubben and El Tahir, 2004). *Capsicum annum* and *Capsicum frutescens* are the most common species in Nigeria. One important constituent of pepper is an alkaloid which serves as a digestive stimulant that is used in an ointment for the relief of arthritic and neuropathic pains (Stern, 2000). It has been reported that pepper production in Nigeria is mostly found on a large-scale in the Northern part under the irrigation system during the dry season (September–March). Delete *et al.* (2003) reported that rainy season crop (June–September) suffers serious pest and disease damage, limiting the output during the season. In Nigeria, the limiting factors in pepper production and other vegetables include weed management, tillage practices, low-yielding varieties, and sub-optimal planting density (Akinfasoye *et al.*, 2006). Seed demand at present is high and supply is unsatisfactory and expected to continue indefinitely. The foundation of any successful crop production is in the quality of seed sown and their germination potential. The amount of viable seeds that can be produced is of crucial economic importance. The pace of progress therefore will depend upon the seed with which good quality seeds can be adequately multiplied and marketed to promote high seed germination, as degeneration in crop yield as a result of poor germination and seedling emergence may not be unrelated to the seed crop production practices adopted by farmers (Cvetkovic, *et al.*,

2022). Thus, the objective of this research is to evaluate the effect of stages of harvesting and seed storage duration on seed germination and seedling vigour of pepper (*Capsicum annum*).

MATERIALS AND METHODS

A field and laboratory experiment was conducted at the Teaching and Research farm as well as the Plant Breeding and Seed Science laboratory of the Joseph Sarwuan Tarkaa University, Makurdi during the 2023 farming season. The University is located within the Southern Guinea Savannah Agro-Ecological Zone of Nigeria. Seeds of two varieties of hot pepper, Dogo and Rodo were obtained from the Techni Seed Company, Jos, Plateau State.

Two nursery beds were made with each bed measuring 2m x 2m (4m²), the top of each bed was leveled flat and a narrow furrow was made on it. Seeds were drilled into the furrow and lightly covered with soil. Dry grass was used as mulch for the beds before light watering. When the seeds started emerging, the mulch material was removed which allowed for hardening of the seedlings and proper aeration without harm from direct sunlight on the young seedlings. The field was cleared manually using cutlass and small farm implements, the beds were made manually using hoe. Transplanting to ridges on the field was carried out on the third week after sowing on the nursery bed. Only healthy and strong seedlings were transplanted. Seedlings were transplanted in the morning and evening hours to minimize transplanting shock. After transplanting, seedlings were watered to make moisture available and to bind the soil particles together with the roots so that nutrients could be readily drawn by the roots of the seedlings. Dichlorocypermethrin insecticide (Best Trade name) was sprayed at the recommended rate of 75mL in a 15-L knapsack sprayer the second week after

transplanting to mitigate insect pest infestation (Avav and Ayuba, 2006). Tagging of each flower was done as they opened and the date at opening (termed anthesis) was recorded on each tag and was done for each variety. A total of 200 flowers were tagged for the two varieties. Fruits of the two varieties that were developed from the tagged flowers were harvested at 46 days after anthesis DAA (mature green stage), 49 DAA (mature half-red ripe) and 52 DAA (mature full-red ripe). At harvest, seeds were then extracted from the fruits using a clean knife and dried to a safe moisture content of 13%. The dried seeds were used for the laboratory experiment. At 0, 3 and 6 months after harvest, the germination behaviour of the various age groups of the pepper seedlings

was determined by taking four replicates of fifty seeds, each counted from each age group of seeds and placed on germination paper in Petri dishes which was moistened with distilled water. These were arranged in a Completely Randomized Design and replicated three times. Incubation was done at room temperature of about (30°C) for 14 days. Germination count was made for each day and the following was evaluated; seedling height, root length, pre-emergence mortality, seedling vigour, seedling fresh weight, seedling dry weight, percentage germination (calculated using the formula adopted by Fakorede and Ojo, 1981) and seedling vigour which was computed using the formula by Abdul-Baki and Anderson (1973) as follows:

$$G \% = \frac{\text{Total number of seedlings that emerged}}{\text{Total number of seeds sown}} \times 100 \quad (\text{Fakorede and Ojo, 1981})$$

$SV = \text{germination percentage} \times \text{seedling shoot} + \text{root length in cm.}$ (Abdul-Baki and Anderson, 1973)

The data collected on all the parameters were subjected to Analysis of Variance using Minitab 17 software. Significant means were separated using Turkey Pairwise Comparison at 95% level of probability.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The main effect of variety on the seed quality

of hot pepper varieties is presented in Table 1. The result indicated that there was no significant difference between Dogo and Rodo for shoot height (SH), root length (RL), pre-emergence mortality (PREM), seedling vigour (SV), seedling dry weight (SDW) and germination percentage (G%). However, Rodo produced seedling fresh weight (SFW) (0.53) significantly higher than Dogo (0.49).

Table 1: Main Effects of Varieties on Seed Quality of Hot Pepper Varieties

Variety	SH(cm)	RL (cm)	PREM %	SV	SFW(g)	SDW(g)	G %
Dogo	4.19 ^a	2.83 ^a	4.19 ^a	359.53 ^a	0.49 ^b	0.36 ^a	83.33 ^a
Rodo	4.50 ^a	2.83 ^a	4.23 ^a	383.16 ^a	0.53 ^a	0.347 ^a	83.06 ^a

This means that same letter within a column are not statistically significant

Key: SH=Seedling Height; RL=Root Length; PREM%= Pre-emergence Mortality; SV=Seedling Vigour; SFW=Seedling Fresh Weight; SDW=Seedling Dry Weight; GEM%=Germination percentage

The result in Table 2 shows main effect of harvest stages on the seed quality of hot peppers. The result showed that seeds from mature full-red Ripe fruits (52 DAA) had significantly highest seedling height (5.61cm) followed by seeds from mature half-red Ripe fruits with (4.25cm) while mature green 46DAA had the lowest seedling height (3.20). A similar trend was observed for seeds from mature full red ripe showing significantly

longest root length (3.80cm) followed by seeds from mature half red ripe (2.84cm) and the least root length in mature green (1.87). For pre-emergence mortality, seeds from mature green fruits recorded a significantly highest value of 7.42% followed by seeds obtained from mature half-red ripe fruits with 4.02% while seeds from mature full-red ripe fruit showed the least pre-emergence mortality (1.21).

Table 2: Main Effects of Harvest Stages on Seed Quality of Hot Pepper Varieties

Harvest Stage	SH(cm)	RL(cm)	PREM%	SV	SFW(g)	SDW(g)	GEM%
MG (46 DAA)	3.20 ^c	1.87 ^c	7.42 ^a	224.24 ^c	0.46 ^c	0.32 ^b	70.33 ^c
MHRR(49DAA)	4.25 ^b	2.84 ^b	4.02 ^b	355.23 ^b	0.52 ^b	0.36 ^{ab}	83.92 ^b
MFRR(52DAA)	5.61 ^a	3.80 ^a	1.21 ^c	534.58 ^a	0.56 ^a	0.389 ^a	95.33 ^a

*Mean values with the same letter within a column are not statistically significant.

Key: MG= Mature Green; MHRR= Mature Half Red Ripe; MFRR= Mature Full Red Ripe; SH=Seedling Height; RL=Root Length; PREM%= Pre-emergence Mortality; SV=Seedling Vigour; SFW=Seedling Fresh Weight; SDW=Seedling Dry Weight; GEM%=Germination Percentage;

Table 3 shows the main effects of storage duration on the seed quality of hot pepper varieties. The result indicated that seedling fresh weight was significantly highest before storage (0.53g) though not significantly different from 6 months after storage (0.50g)

but was different from 3 months after storage (0.49g). On the other hand, seedling dry weight was significantly highest before storage (0.38g) which did not differ significantly from 3 months after storage (0.35g)but was different from 6 months after storage (0.34g).

Table 3: Main Effects of Storage Duration on Seed Quality of Hot Pepper Varieties

Storage Duration	SH(cm)	RL(cm)	PREM%	SV	SFW(g)	SDW(g)	GEM%
Before Storage	4.34 ^a	2.958 ^a	4.083 ^a	372.76 ^a	0.534 ^a	0.382 ^a	83.83 ^a
3 months after Storage	4.34 ^a	2.755 ^a	4.333 ^a	367.90 ^a	0.499 ^{ab}	0.348 ^{ab}	82.67 ^a
6 Months after Storage	4.38 ^a	2.796 ^a	4.229 ^a	373.39 ^a	0.504 ^{ab}	0.335 ^b	83.08 ^a

*Means with same letter within a column are not statistically significant

Key: SH=Seedling height; RL=Root Length; PREM%= Pre emergence mortality; SV=Seedling Vigour; SFW=Seedling Fresh Weight; SDW=Seedling Dry Weight; GEM%=Germination Percentage;

The main effects of harvest stages x storage duration interaction on root length of hot pepper varieties are presented in Table 4. The table showed that seeds from mature full-red ripe fruits produced significantly lengthiest roots before storage although not different from seeds from mature half-red ripe fruits but were significantly different from mature green. At 3 months after

storage, seeds from mature full-red ripe fruits recorded the lengthiest roots which were significantly different from mature half-red ripe and mature green. However, root length in mature half-red ripe (2.54) was not significantly different from mature green (1.91). A similar trend was observed in 6 months after harvest.

Table 4: Main Effects of Harvest Stages x Storage Duration Interaction on Root Length of Hot Pepper Varieties

Harvest Stage	Before Storage (cm)	3 Months (cm)	6 Months (cm)
Mature Green (46 DAA)	1.62 ^c	1.91 ^c	2.10 ^c
Mature Half Red Ripe (49 DAA)	3.37 ^{ab}	2.54 ^{bc}	2.60 ^{bc}
Mature Full Red Ripe (52 DAA)	3.89 ^a	3.82 ^a	3.69 ^a

*Means with the same letter within a column are not statistically significant

This study revealed that the mature full red ripe stage of harvest gave the highest germination percentage and vigour for the two varieties of pepper. This agrees with the findings of Khatun *et al.*, (2009) who reported that the highest germination percentage, root length, shoot length and vigour index were observed in BARI masur-4 that were harvested at full red ripe stage. He also stated that the harvesting stage had a significant effect on some seed quality parameters such as percentage of germination, speed of germination, and seedling vigour. The general conclusion is that the more mature the seed is, the greater its vigour and potential to become established as a seedling.

High pre-emergence mortality observed at the mature green stage in this study could be accounted for variations that exist between seed lots since the seeds are not equally matured (Aloho *et al.*, 2002). Kortse *et al.* (2017) state that in fleshy

fruits, the highest quality seed may be obtained from fruits harvested at edible maturity but before the onset of severe decomposition. Therefore, seeds must be harvested at the correct stage of development to obtain maximum viability and vigour. Shaheb *et al.* (2015) observed that seeds from fully ripe fruits had greater germination rates than those obtained from half-ripe or orange coloured fruits of pepper.

Storage durations show no significant effect throughout the study. According to Christensen (2018), a pepper seed when properly dried and stored, can remain viable for up to 25 years, but 2 to 5 years is the more realistic time frame. Julio (2011) stated that the original concepts about seed longevity led to the suggestion that short-lived seeds will remain viable for less than 3 years and long-lived seeds for more than 15 years. He also reported that seeds of the same species retain viability after drying to relatively low seed water content while

others are extremely sensitive to loss of water usually associated with short-lived seeds. Several factors have been reported to be responsible for the longevity of seeds. Robin *et al.*, (2012) gave initial viability as a factor that determines the longevity of a seed.

CONCLUSION

It was observed from the study that different stages of harvest had profound effects on the germination of hot peppers regardless of variety. Seeds from fruits harvested at the full-red ripe stage of maturity and from the half-red ripe stage were better in quality than those from the mature green stage. Fruit harvested at mature full red ripe stage of maturity produces seeds with the highest germination while early harvest resulted in

poor germination. Storage duration shows no significant effect for most germination and seed parameters except in seedling dry weight throughout all the periods of storage. To increase the seed quality performance of hot peppers, it is essential to obtain seeds from fruits harvested at the mature red ripe stage for maximum seed quality. Farmers can store their pepper seeds for up to six (6) months without fear of losing their viability. It is also imperative to verify these results in different locations using different varieties.

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